

Privacy-preserving Attribute Based Credentials for 6G networks

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Abstract—This paper provides an overview of the integration of privacy preserving Attribute Based Credentials (p-ABC) into the 3GPP 5G Advanced system as well as into the European Project RIGOUROUS (secuRe desIGn and deplOyment of trUsthwoRthy cOntinUum computing 6G Services) for 6G. The differences in the access and device (or user) authentication and authorization in the 3GPP system and the concepts of p-ABC require architectural changes in the main procedures. The novel architecture and procedures of p-ABC support in 5G Advanced are described along with an overview of the 6G RIGOUROUS architecture highlighting the updated zero-touch onboarding of devices into the system. This integration enhances the 5G+ system to support privacy goals such as minimal disclosure or controlled linkability through zero-knowledge proofs.

Index Terms—6G, 3GPP, ABC, Zero Knowledge Proof, Privacy Preserving, Security

I. INTRODUCTION

Privacy preserving Attribute Based Credentials (p-ABC) are digital certificates that allow the owner to disclose only the minimum information necessary to prove his access right to a resource or service. For every resource, a policy defines what attributes are necessary to be proofed to permit the access to it. For instance, the policy could demand to proof the requester is over certain years old, e.g. “over 18 years old? yes or no”. By using p-ABC certificate, the owner could proof the possession of the property without disclosing the actual value of the attribute. ABC frameworks, as described in [1]–[4] require certain actors (user, issuer, verifier, revocation authority, registry, inspector). This authentication and authorization (AA) scheme is omitted on the current mobile networks. But its integration is feasible and empowers with privacy the 6G perception. Currently, AA of 5G is based on a shared secret between the user and the system, kept in both sides in a tamper proof environment, the USIM, and in the Subscription Database of the mobile network. Therefore, subscriptions belongs to a certain mobile network operator. To use other mobile networks services, roaming procedure enable remote authentication to users, where the shared secret never leaves the home operator. Only derived keys are provided to the serving network for performing the security of the access stratum (AS) and non access stratum (NAS) protocols. In our work, we design the integration of p-ABCs in future networks, the subscriber does not need to belong to any network operator, but instead may purchase “attributes” to

access different services, including cellular networks. The issuer will grant the user with a p-ABC credential, which later can use to authenticate against the service providers. Thanks to the use of the p-ABC technology, this process can be carried out in a privacy-preserving way, particularly against the network the user is accessing to. Enabling advanced privacy-preserving techniques is a fundamental need for the incipient designs for 6G networks. To this aim, this paper describes the innovative approach for integrating p-ABC methodologies into the 3GPP system, enhancing with privacy the regular USIM based access of current networks [5].

The remaining of this paper is organized as follows. Section II provides an overview of the current state of the art regarding the concept of p-ABC in general. Section III elaborates the related work on p-ABC and Section IV describes the integration of the p-ABC concepts into the 5G Advanced architecture and procedures. Section V overviews the 6G RIGOUROUS [6] system including p-ABC for device onboarding. Finally, Section VI concludes the paper.

II. OVERVIEW OF P-ABC CONCEPT

The p-ABC framework requires that all participants in the framework actors (user, issuer, verifier, revocation authority, registry, inspector) provide their public key in a registry, which may be a decentralized ledger such as a blockchain, in line with current decentralization and self-sovereignty trends. All parties will have access to this information, so that they can retrieve the corresponding public keys of the other participants in the communication, if required.

The relationship between all p-ABC entities is shown in Figure 1. Note that, in specific instantiating of an p-ABC system, some of the roles, such as inspection and revocation authority, may be assumed by the same entity. The user retrieves a credential from the Issuer, who is also exchanging information with the Revocation Authority to set the revocation information for the credential. The User can use the credential to generate presentation tokens for the Verifier, who can ask the Inspector for token inspection and the Revocation Authority for the revocation information. The credential can be revoked if e.g. it is misused, expires or some parameters are exceeded. The prerequisite for the network access is the retrieval of suitable p-ABC credentials from the p-ABC Issuer after the onboarding procedure, i.e. devices can connect to a onboarding

Fig. 1. ABC entities and interaction

network for authentication and secure connection setup as well the secure provisioning of the long term credentials. The devices are initially attaching to an onboarding network with default credentials and then retrieve their long-term credentials in form of privacy-preserving Attribute Based Credentials from a provisioning sever. The p-ABC credentials can be seen as a digital identity of the device that can be used for different purposes such as authenticate itself in untrusted sub-networks or derive proofs of its attributes that might be needed to access to net-apps, 6G services, an even to authenticate and access directly to other previously unknown devices (as long as they also trust the Issuer) in a D2D interaction. To achieve selective linkability, a user may generate a pseudonym from the public key embedded in the credential during the presentation the credential to the verifier, i.e. service owner. In our setting, the device may generate an unlimited number of pseudonyms from the public key as shown in Figure 2. Particularly, scope-exclusive pseudonyms [7] present an interesting alternative, as they can be reused for scopes based, e.g., on the verifier identity and timing data, while remaining unlinkable with any other pseudonym generated by the user.

III. RELATED WORK

Various work has been carried out for digital identities, from which the biggest focus in recent years is the paradigm of Self Sovereign Identities (SSI), with emphasis on achieving privacy and control by individuals. Privacy-preserving Attribute Based Credentials (p-ABC) systems target to establish privacy-friendly identity management systems fulfilling the requirements of selective disclosure, unlinkability, and security [3]. Zero-knowledge proofs are the underlying privacy-enhancing technology to allow a user to prove possession of a credential with certain attributes to a service provider (verifier), who can verify its validity without requiring that the user discloses the full credential. Additionally, they enable unlinkability so that for any two proofs are it cannot be determined whether the same or a different user produced them. During the presentation phase, confidentiality can be achieved

Fig. 2. Pseudonym Generation

by establishing a secure encrypted channel between user and the service provider in any traditional way. Apart from the basic functionality, researches have worked in extensions to security and privacy features. The authors in [8] provide an enhanced solution for p-ABC with the advantages of a data minimization cryptographic scheme, unlinkability between the different authentication sessions and the feature that the derivation of certified attributes by the issuing authority relies on a non interactive protocol. In [9], the authors propose a solution where the specific issuer of a credential is hidden, and instead a verifier will only know that one of the members of an accepted pool of issuers generated the credential. The authors in [4] discuss a distributed p-ABC system with decentralized issuance, range proofs, pseudonyms, inspection and revocation. 3GPP in their currently ongoing Release 19, i.e. 5G-Advanced, is also looking into the user identification and the respective authentication architecture [10] with different studies. The user aspects are a new dimension from 3GPP perspective since up to now, only the User Equipment (UE, device with USIM) is authenticated with the network based on the 3GPP authentication protocols e.g. EAP-AKA' or 5G-AKA in 5G [5]. The corresponding security study work in [11] is not completed at the time of this paper, but could benefit from the p-ABC concepts. The agreements under discussions were with respect to the identification of the Human User of a Subscription and the privacy and user consent aspects with respect to exposure of User Identity Profile Information. No agreements are currently available on the key issue of authentication and authorization of Users and Restrictions on Users.

IV. P-ABC INTEGRATION INTO 5G ADVANCED

The credential issuance procedure is an essential prerequisite for the p-ABC integration into the 3GPP system. It is

assumed that the communication between UE and Issuer is performed over a secure IPsec connection. Two key parameters are essential for a subscription in the 3GPP system, the root key and the subscription identity. The generation of both parameters is triggered by the Issuer and processed by a Key Generation Function. In that way the quality of the key material can be assured, and potential duplications of subscription identities can be avoided. The Credential Issuance procedure is shown in the following Figure 3 and described below in each steps.

- 1) The UE with the help of the User generates Private Key K_{Upr} and a corresponding Public Key K_{Upu} .
- 2) The UE with the help of the User generates a credential i.e. adding attributes such as device identity, network type, network name, public key, random number and may have additional attributes e.g. user family and given names, user birthday, residential address, bank account etc. The UE may generate a proof that it holds the private key of the included public key of the credential. The UE may have a general 3GPP mobile network subscription or Non-3GPP network subscription. The Random Number may be included in the credential and may be used to compute the proof of the private key of the UE. The device ID from the UE may be included, e.g. the Permanent Equipment Identifier (PEI), to bind also the credential to a specific device (this may be required for legal interception).
- 3) The UE sends a Credential Issuance Request to the Issuer. This message may be protected with the IPsec connection between UE and Issuer. The User might have subscribed or is in the process to subscribe online to the 3GPP/Non-3GPP network access of different packages of different providers, e.g. 10 Gbit for one week at operator XY, the Credential Issuance Request may include this information, which is later included in the revocation credential. This step may be like the purchase operation of a web shop with defining the contract details.
- 4) The Issuer verifies the information in the credential e.g. with other means like checking the passport information or the purchasing information. The Issuer sets the revocation parameters of the credential according to the service the User purchased.
- 5) The Issuer sends a Key Generation Request to the Key Generation Function (KGF) including the UE Public Key K_{Upu} .
- 6) The KGF generates a pair of root key K_{Root} and subscription identity SUPI. The generated root key K_{Root} may be equivalent to the CK, IK or the (E)MSK as defined in TS 33.501. The KGF encryptes the root key K_{Root} with the public key of the UE/User K_{Upu} , i.e. $EncK_{Root}K_{Upu}$.
- 7) The Key Generation Function sends the encrypted root key K_{Root} to the Issuer.
- 8) The Issuer sends a Credential Revocation Issuance Request to the Revocation Authority with the credential and the revocation parameters, e.g. additional information about the service, remaining data volume, remaining time etc..
- 9) The Revocation Authority verifies and stores the revocation credential and signs it with the Revocation Authority Private Key K_{PriReA} , i.e. $SignedRevocationAttributeK_{PriReA}$.

Fig. 3. Credential Issuance

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- 9) The Revocation Authority verifies and stores the revocation credential and signs it with the Revocation Authority Private Key K_{PriReA} , i.e. $SignedRevocationAttributeK_{PriReA}$.

- 10) The Revocation Authority provides the signed revocation credential back to the Issuer.
- 11) The Issuer includes the encrypted root key K_{Root} in one attribute in the credential. The Issuer signs the attributes of the credential.
- 12) The Issuer responds to the UE with a Credential Issuance Response containing the signed credential by the Issuer and includes the signed revocation credential by the Revocation Authority. The UE can now decrypt the root key pair and subscription identity with the private key.

In order to access a service in a 3GPP network, the device needs to be registered to the system. The following call flow in Figure 4 shows the registration procedure using the p-ABC credential for authentication and registration to the network. As a prerequisite the UE is provisioned with the p-ABC credential from the Issuer as described in Figure 3. When accessing another network, the UE needs to request a new credential with a fresh K_{Root} key to achieve unlinkability. The UE does not have a SUCI, since the SUCI always points to a UDM Instance where the SUPI is located, but since the UE is not a real subscriber of the mobile network, there is no data record in the UDM for the subscription such as SUPI and root key. The SUPI is instead generated as a new pseudonym from the user public key each time the UE is connecting to a new serving network.

- 1) The UE sends a NAS Registration Request to the AMF, indicating that it wants to connect with p-ABC credentials. The UE may include an anonymous SUCI (e.g. anonymous@operator.xy) with the NAI of the network.
- 2) The AMF replies with a NAS Response and the presentation policy for registering to the network with p-ABC credentials. The policy may require the UE to construct the presentation token in a specific way and to include specific attributes which are important for the mobile network operator. Those required attributes may be but not limited to: encrypted SUPI, encrypted Root Key, Issuer Public Key, Revocation parameters, requested services (IP connectivity, IMS Services, etc.), QoS profile etc. The AMF also includes a public key from the AUSF.
- 3) The UE will create a presentation token according to the policy. The UE may include a proof that it holds the private key and respective information for the verification e.g. random number. The UE selects the encrypted Root Key K_{Root} from the KGF according to the credential previously issued from the Issuer and generates a new pseudonym from its public key which is used as a SUPI for this mobile network. The UE decrypts the K_{Root} with its private key K_{Upr} . The UE then encrypts the pseudonym, i.e. SUPI, and the Root Key K_{Root} , with the public key of the AUSF.
- 4) The UE sends a NAS request to the AMF including the presentation token and the encrypted SUPI and Root Key K_{Root} .
- 5) The AMF checks the validity of the presentation token.

Fig. 4. Network Registration with p-ABC Credentials

This is done by verifying the signatures of the attributes signed by the Issuer with the public key of the Issuer K_{PupIss} . The AMF may also check the proof of the private key of the UE with the pseudonym in the credentials.

- 6) The AMF sends a Verify Revocation Information Request to the Revocation Authority. The message may be sent via the NEF. The request may contain, if

Fig. 5. RIGOUROUS High-level Functional Block Architecture (HLFA)

needed, part of the presentation token from the UE, e.g. revocation attributes signed by the Revocation Authority.

- 7) The Revocation Authority verifies the request from the AMF with the stored information at the time the credential was issued by the Issuer and whether the credential is still valid. The Revocation Authority provides in the Verify Revocation Information Response the result back to the AMF, i.e. whether the credential is still active and potentially additional information about the service, e.g. remaining data volume, remaining time etc.
- 8) If the credential is not revoked, the AMF/SEAF sends a Nausf_UEAuthentication_Authenticate Request message to the AUSF including the presentation token and the encrypted attributes related to the root key and the subscription identity.
- 9) The AUSF verifies the request and the presentation token and decrypts the encrypted attributes, i.e. at least Root Key K_{Root} and subscription identity SUPI. The AUSF does not query the UDM and selects the authentication method. EAP-AKA' would be most suitable depending on whether the user purchased p-ABC credential access with non-3GPP networks and uses the p-ABC credential access also on devices not supporting the NAS protocol. There is further no need to query the UDM for de-concealment of the SUPI since the user

is not a subscriber of the mobile operators, thus does not have a record in the UDM and the AUSF is taking care of decryption of the Root Key and the SUPI. The AUSF creates an authentication challenge as per normal operation and specified in 3GPP TS 33.501 [3].

- 10) The AUSF sends a Nausf_UEAuthentication_Authenticate Response to the AMF/SEAF including the authentication challenge.
- 11) The AMF/SEAF sends the authentication challenge to the UE in a NAS message. The AMF/SEAF includes a Presentation Token Success indication in the NAS Message.
- 12) The UE computes the authentication result from the authentication challenge as per normal operation specified in TS 33.501 [3].
- 13) The UE completes the authentication procedure as per normal operation and AUSF and UE derive the keys accordingly.
- 14) The AMF/SEAF perform the NAS Security Mode Command procedure as per normal operation.
- 15) After the all security procedures are completed, the AMF sends a NAS Registration Accept message to the UE including the 5G-GUTI. The UE will use the 5G-GUTI as in normal operation for further requests.

V. P-ABC IN THE 6G RIGOUROUS ARCHITECTURE

The RIGOUROUS architecture in Figure 5 is fully described in [12] with the main architectural pillars: Zero-touch network and Service Management (Automated and Closed Loop Operation), zero trust by design, SOAR cycle (Security - Orchestration - Automation - Response), DevSecOps, and AIaaS (Artificial Intelligence as a Service). The target is to achieve cyber-attack response and mitigation with various technologies such as end to end (E2E) network slicing over 6G networks, AI-driven adaptive decision-making based on attack information, infrastructure status, and contextual information as well as implementing the DevSecOps paradigm. SOAR cycle of the project simplifies the threat and vulnerability management, incident response, and security operations automation. The RIGOUROUS framework addresses the main stages of DevSecOps, encompassing the design/development of services and their security-privacy requirements, devices onboarding specification, automated provisioning and onboarding of security-privacy requirements, real-time operation reconfiguration, management, and maintenance. The related feature in [13] is on IoT bootstrapping and onboarding, which designs the zero-touch device bootstrapping and respectively the trusted application onboarding. The specification enables a secure connection setup of the IoT devices with long-term credentials and describes how to prevent harmful applications for being installed in the IoT devices. The long-term credentials are realized as Privacy-preserving Attribute-Based Credentials, providing minimal disclosure, unlinkability and trustworthy certification of attributes. The p-ABC credentials can be used for different purposes in RIGOUROUS as shown in [14] such as authentication in untrusted sub-networks, to derive proofs of its attributes that might be needed for accessing network applications, specific 6G services, and even to authenticate and access directly other previously unknown devices in a device to device (D2D) interaction (as long as they also trust the Issuer). The p-ABC credentials in the proposal are built around the NANCY (An Artificial Intelligent Aided Unified Network for Secure Beyond 5G Long Term Evolution) Identity (ID) [15]. The proposed solution in clause V of this paper will be used in RIGOUROUS for the IoT bootstrapping and onboarding with the NANCY ID and will be further enhanced to cover all the scenarios, including the trusted application onboarding. For the upcoming 6G study phase in 3GPP in Release 20 and onwards, it is envisioned that the p-ABC concepts will be discussed with the respective 6G (user) privacy improvements and security architecture evolution.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

The p-ABC based authentication mechanism allows to authenticate different attributes about an entity flexibly and selectively without revealing additional information about the entity by means of zero-knowledge proofs. Most of the authentication means available related to authentication of attributes classically require full and unique authentication of an entity. For example, attributes (like age) could be put into a certificate together with name of the user, email address,

public key, and other data about that entity. To corroborate an attribute (for example, that the user is an adult) the certificate has to be presented and all information have to be revealed. This is not considered a privacy-preserving solution. However cryptographic solutions, like attribute-based credentials, enable to build more secure and yet privacy-friendly identity management systems and can be a potential candidate for the evolving business and service models which demands more privacy friendly solutions. The solution proposed in this paper can be smoothly integrated into the control plane signalling of the current authentication procedure of 5G, but requires enhancements with respect of the ABC framework with all involved actors. The issuance of credentials is based on secure communication path between the UE and the Issuer, i.e. a user plane connection with respective strong transport layer security. Future work is carried out on integrating different network types and services into the framework, as well as the management and details of the credential and NANCY ID handling.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work was supported in part by the EU's HE research and innovation program HORIZON-JU-SNS-2022 under the RIGOUROUS project (Grant No. 101095933).

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